

INFORMATION LITERACY

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Abstract

Information Literacy is very important for the students especially in higher education. It helps to develop critical thinking and research skills in them, through literature review the paper highlights the role played by the librarians in motivating such skills in their students. There will be different levels of information literacy instruction for different types of students. The orientation programmes are organized for new/fresh Users, whereas users Education is imparted to all users.

Keywords: *Information Literacy, Literacy Skills, Literacy Models, Literacy.*

1. Introduction

The phrase “information literacy” was first used by Paul Zurkowski (the then President of the US Information Industry Association) in 1974, in a proposal submitted to the National Commission on Libraries and Information Science (NCLIS). Information is a fundamental resources for supporting and enhancing teaching, learning research activities in Educational Institutions. In this context. Information literacy plays a vital role in educating the users of Libraries to know about various information sources and more specifically where and how to search desired information to the right reader; the libraries should develop information literacy competency development programmes which will make the users information literate. Though. ‘Information Literacy ‘embraces the related concepts

like user education, library instruction, bibliographic instruction, and library research, It has broader perspectives and wider applications than these concepts.

2. Definitions

1. 'Information Literacy' is "the ability to recognize when information is needed and have the ability to locate, evaluate and use effectively the needed information".
[<http://en.wikipedia.org>]
2. 'Information Literacy' is a combination of knowledge and skills essential to analyze information need, locate probable information resources. Evaluate access tools, design search stagy and assess information contents.

3. Need for Information Literacy

Due to information explosion, the information is being published with its ever. Increasing growth. The emergence of changing media of information viz. Print to electronic resources and ICT applications in libraries have a great impact on storage and retrieval of information. The information is generated through variety of documents and disseminated by various formal and informal channels of ~ communication of information. Such decentralization / deinstitutionalization of information facilitate users to acquire their information irrespective of baiters like geographical barrier or non- availability of information. Such access to any remote place promotes use of information by users whenever and wherever desired by them. In this ever changing present environment of information, to acquire exact information, the users need to have certain knowledge. The lack of users' information literacy and lack of users' awareness about ICT applications in library Tarie Senforce the libraries to conduct information literacy.

4. Criteria for an Effective Information Literacy Programme

To be effective, Information literacy instruction and assessment must be comprehensive in scope and reach all the students who graduate from our institutions. There will be different levels of information literacy instruction for different types of students. Undergraduates in technical fields will require a different

type of information literacy instruction from undergraduates in the liberal arts. Freshman and sophomores will need to be taught the basics of information literacy and receive instruction from a multi or cross disciplinary perspective. Juniors, seniors and graduate students will need more specialized instruction related to their major and fields of research.

5. Fundamentals of Information Literacy in the Process of Lifelong Learning.

From the users point of view. There are some basic skills which are essential for them to make them information literate. So, that they can achieve lifelong learning. The following are some of the fundamental activities: the users are supposed to undertake for lifelong learning.

- To recognize value of information.
- To recognize own information needs
- To know various collections of information sources.
- Organization of these collections.
- Use of library catalogue/OPAC
- Locate and Access an information
- Use of E-sources, Internet, Library Networks, Websites, E-mail.

The users as well as well as library professionals must know that technology improves to information and not an intellectual Access. Intellectual Access exclusively depends upon one's skills and abilities and it differs to individual which is fundamental means in the process of lifelong learning.

6. Information Literacy Programmes

6.1. User Orientation and User Education

The activities like user 'User Orientation' and 'User Education' are the part of Information literacy Programme to guide, instruct and assist the users for getting their information. The orientation is organized for new/fresh Users, whereas users Education is imparted to all users. These activities enhance abilities of users for independent search, evaluation and use of information, evaluation and use of information.

Literacy Programme is a Joint enterprise of library staff and users. The

lectures (Audio-Visual) for Information Literacy should be Users Centered activities like book talks, exhibitions, counseling on complex information sources and their use and library services etc. should be user focused.

6.2 Users club for Improving Information Literacy

The NAAC guidelines (2006) emphasize that the better relations between library staff and users can increase use of library resources and inculcate reading habits. The users club is a constitution of users comprising of representative library users of this club under the Chairmanship of Librarian. The activities to undertaken by such club are: experts' lectures on use of Libraries & reading habits, talks on popular books and reviews, exhibitions of information resources, demonstration on how to use catalogues/OPAC, Internet, on-line searching etc

7. Information Literacy Models

Model No.1

Model No. 2

8. Advantages of Information Literacy Programme

The carefully planned and successfully carried out information literacy programmes benefit the users as under.

- The users can determine the Nature and Extent of their information needs.
- They can critically evaluate their sources of information and independently get a prompt an accurate access to desired information.
- The users can develop their information search skills and satisfied users intend to revisit the library and advise others to visit.
- Information Literacy Programme facilitates extensive use of library resources and services and promotes Group Dynamics of users.
- Information Literacy is the necessity of the present Information Age as information is one of the fundamental resources for Industrial. Agricultural,

